

CHARACTERIZATION OF STRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF CLAY/EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: A three-roll mill machine was used to disperse and exfoliate the clay nanoparticles in an epoxy matrix. Two types of clay particles were used: Nanomer I.28E from Nanocor, Inc. and Cloisite® 30B from Southern Clay Products, Inc. The compounding process was carried out with varying concentrations of clay particles (1 to 10 wt.%). XRD and TEM were used to characterize the morphology of the nanocomposites. The Nanomer I.28E/epoxy showed an ordered intercalated structure with a d-spacing of 3.6 nm, whereas the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy showed a disordered intercalated structure with a d-spacing greater than 5 nm. Consistently, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy nanocomposites showed higher elastic modulus compared to the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy nanocomposites and this can be directly related to the higher degree of intercalation/exfoliation that occurred in the former case. It was also observed that both nanocomposites showed higher modulus with higher clay content. The incorporation of clay particles also gave rise to a considerable amount increment of storage modulus with increasing clay content. Overall, the compounding process with a three-roll mill proved to be effective in producing good intercalation/exfoliation of clay platelets in an epoxy matrix.

KEYWORDS: Nanocomposites, montmorillonite clay, TEM, mechanical behavior, thermomechanical behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, polymer based silicate nanocomposites have drawn significant attention due to its substantial improvement in mechanical, thermal and barrier properties over the unmodified polymer [1-13]. Typically, the nanosize clay used in a polymer matrix is a silicate-based montmorillonite. It has a platy structure with individual platelets having thickness of 1 nm and surface lengths on the order of 100 and 1000 nm. The montmorillonite clay is hydrophilic in nature and therefore, requires surface modification to be organically compatible with the hydrophobic polymer resin [3]. In general, the existing cations in the silicate, typically Na⁺ or K⁺, are exchanged for organic cations, such as alkyl ammonium cations [3]. In some cases this cation can also act as an initiator for in situ polymerization. Alternatively, polymer can be introduced into the silicate layers from either a solution or a melt. In general, the improvement of properties of these nanocomposites depends directly on the degree of exfoliation i.e., the amount of surface area of clay particles exposed to the polymeric material.

One of the advantages of clay nanocomposites is that it can be processed using the conventional techniques. However, a homogeneous dispersion and complete exfoliation of clay platelets in a polymeric matrix is a challenge. This is mainly due to the high viscosity of the resin and the strong tendency of nanoclay particles to agglomerate [4]. The other factors that can affect the degree of exfoliation are the structure of clays, curing temperature and curing agent [5]. The commonly used techniques to process clay-epoxy nanocomposites are: direct mixing and solution mixing [5-7]. However, these techniques produce mainly intercalated structure as discussed before [8]. Vaia et al. have suggested that the degree of exfoliation can be improved through the aid of conventional shear devices such as extruders, mixers,

ultrasonicators etc. [9]. Accordingly, Yasmin et al. [10] have reported the success in using a three-roll mill as a means of applying external shearing forces to disperse and exfoliate the stacked layers of montmorillonite in an epoxy matrix. In the present study, nanocomposites were prepared with two different types of clay nanoparticles with a three-roll mill under the identical conditions. This study also shows a comparison between Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B reinforced epoxy nanocomposites with regard to their morphology, mechanical and thermomechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

A diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin cured with methyl tetrahydrophthalic anhydride hardener from Vantico was used as the matrix. 1-Methylimidazole was used as an accelerator. They were in proportions of 100:90:1 (phr) respectively. The reinforcing clay nanoparticles were Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B, commercially available from Nanocor, Inc. and Southern Clay Products, Inc., respectively. Both of them are natural montmorillonite (MMT) and were subjected to surface modification treatment with a methyl, tallow, bis-2-hydroxyethyl, quaternary ammonium to make them organophilic. The physical properties of both clay particles [14-15] are available in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of clay particles

Physical properties	Cloisite® 30B [14]	Nanomer I.28E [15]
Color	Off white	White
Density, g/cc	1.98	1.90
d-spacing (d_{001}), Å	18.5	>20
Aspect ratio	200-1000	200-500
Surface area, m ² /g	750	750
Mean particle size, μ	6	8-10

Fabrication

A three-roll mill machine (Model 52M 2.5" x 5") from Ross, USA was used to disperse and exfoliate the clay nanoparticles in the epoxy resin. First, the epoxy resin (DGEBA) was placed between the feed and the center rolls. Once the rolls started moving, the clay particles were spread gradually on the resin to achieve maximum contact with the rolls. At the beginning of the mixing, the epoxy resin became viscous and opaque due to the incorporation of clay particles. However, when the dispersion was completed, it produced a clear and transparent solution. It is assumed that the dispersion was achieved in two steps. First, the external shear forces generated between the adjacent rolls dispersed the particles as smaller tactoids. Second, the combined shear and diffusion processes facilitated the separation and penetration of polymer between clay platelets to form either an intercalated or exfoliated structure. Compounding was carried out at room temperature for 3 h, with a rotation speed of 500 rpm and a feed rate of 120 g/h. The final product from the mill was then collected and mixed with the hardener at 60°C for 1 h on a hot plate. After adding accelerator and mixing for a few minutes, the solution was left overnight for degassing. After degassing, the mixture was poured in an aluminum mold and cured in an oven at 148°C for 1 h. Nanocomposites were prepared with clay contents from 1 to 10 wt.%.

Characterization

Small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) was performed on both clay and cured samples to detect the diffraction peaks and the corresponding d_{001} -spacing between clay platelets. SAXS was carried out on a Bruker AXS solid-state detector with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.541 \text{ \AA}$) and operating at 30 kV and 13 mA. The 2D-diffraction pattern for each sample was collected for 1.5 h. For further confirmation of d-spacing and the degree of intercalation/exfoliation, a JEOL TEM operating at an accelerating voltage of 100 kV was used. The ultrathin TEM samples with a thickness of 60 nm were cut using a microtome at room temperature. The tensile samples were tested on an Instron 8500 servohydraulic machine at a crosshead rate of 0.127 mm/min. The fracture surfaces of tensile specimens were examined using a Hitachi S4500 FE SEM. The fracture surfaces were examined at 3 kV accelerating voltage and were gold coated prior to SEM investigation to avoid charging. The thermomechanical behavior of nanocomposites was studied using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (2980 model TA Instruments, USA). The experiments were carried out on rectangular samples (80 mm x 7.5 mm x 2.5 mm) under dual cantilever mode. A frequency of 1 Hz, a static force of 0.1 N and an amplitude of 15 μm with a temperature ramp of 3°C/min and a scanning temperature range from 30 to 200°C were employed. The glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined from the peak of the $\tan \delta$ curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphology

The SAXS patterns of all cured nanocomposites containing varying concentration of Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B are shown in Fig. 1a and 1b, respectively. The diffraction patterns for both pure Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B are also shown in these figures for comparison. While Nanomer I.28E shows a characteristic diffraction peak corresponding to d_{001} plane at 24 \AA (2.4 nm), Cloisite® 30B shows the d_{001} plane at 18 \AA (1.8 nm). From Fig. 1a, it can be seen that all nanocomposites reinforced with Nanomer

Fig. 1. SAXS patterns of nanocomposites with varying clay contents. (a) Nanomer I.28E; (b) Cloisite® 30B.

I.28E show the diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 2.45^\circ$ corresponding to $d_{001}=3.6 \text{ nm}$, which is about 50% higher than the initial value of Nanomer I.28E (2.4 nm). However, as the clay content increases, the intensity of the peak increases and this can be correlated to the higher amount of ordered intercalates with higher clay

contents. The lower d-spacing (3.53 nm) for the 10 wt.% Nanomer I.28E/epoxy composite compared to the low clay content nanocomposites can be attributed to the increased intercalating sites in the former case which might impede further apart of individual platelets. It is to be noted that the WAXD patterns of nanocomposites containing 1 to 10 wt.% of Nanomer I.28E (except 2 wt.%) also showed peaks at the same basal spacing range as in the present study [8]. However, the occurrence of peak in the SAXS pattern of 2 wt.% Nanomer I.28E/epoxy composite confirms the presence of a shallow peak. Since the error for WAXD is about 5% and the applied scanning speed was too high, 0.5°/min, the SAXS result should be considered more accurate. In contrast with Nanomer I.28E/epoxy, none of the nanocomposites reinforced with Cloisite® 30B shows any peak, as shown in Fig. 1b. This is an indication of exfoliation or disordered intercalation with a d-spacing higher than 7 nm.

Fig. 2. TEM images of 5 wt.% clay nanocomposites at low mag. (a) Nanomer I.28E; (b) Cloisite® 30B.

Fig. 3. TEM images of clay nanocomposites at high mag. (a) 1 wt.% Nanomer I.28E; (b) 10 wt.% Cloisite® 30B.

The TEM images of nanocomposites containing 5 wt.% of Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B are shown in Figs. 2a and 2b, respectively. Both nanocomposites show intercalates, however, the Cloisite 30B/epoxy shows waviness and homogeneous dispersion compared to the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy. The TEM images of 1 wt.% Nanomer I.28E/epoxy and 10 wt.% Cloisite® 30B/epoxy at high magnification are shown in Fig. 3a and 3b, respectively. The dark lines in these figures are the intersection of clay platelets of 1 nm thickness. While the 1 wt.% Nanomer I.28E/epoxy (Fig. 3a) shows stacks of ordered intercalates with an

average d-spacing of 3.10 nm, the 10 wt.% Cloisite® 30B/epoxy shows stacks of disordered intercalates with an average d-spacing of higher than 5 nm. However, the absence of peak in the case of Cloisite® 30B (Fig. 1b) instead of 5 nm d-spacing can be attributed to the misaligned and wavy intercalates (Fig. 3b). It is to be noted that the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy composites with lower clay content showed basal spacing higher than 8 nm as discussed elsewhere [10]. These results are, therefore, in good agreement with the SAXS results. The occurrence of ordered intercalates with a low d-spacing even in 1 wt.% Nanomer I.28E/epoxy and disordered intercalates with a higher d-spacing even in 10 wt.% Cloisite® 30B/epoxy suggests that the degree of intercalation/exfoliation depends on the type of clay and its surface modification. From Fig. 3, it is also observed that the average length of Nanomer I.28E is higher (~180 nm) than the Cloisite® 30B (~90 nm). The lower aspect ratio after mixing can be attributed to the milling process, which breaks the clay particles during mixing.

It is of interest to mention that under the direct and solution mixing methods, the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy also showed an ordered intercalated structure but with an average d-spacing lower than that obtained in the shear mixing method [8]. Therefore, it can be noted that the nanocomposites reinforced with Nanomer I.28E (Nanacor, Inc.) always produces ordered intercalated structure, whereas the nanocomposites reinforced with Cloisite® 30B always produces a combination of disordered intercalated and exfoliated structure regardless of clay content.

Mechanical behavior

The elastic modulus as a function of clay content is shown in Fig. 4a. It is found that the modulus of the nanocomposites increases continuously with increasing clay content. Up to 2 wt.% of clay, both Nanomer I.28E- and Cloisite 30B/epoxy shows the similar modulus values, however, at higher clay content, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy shows a continuous increment of modulus over the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy nanocomposites. A decreasing rate of modulus improvement with higher clay content is also observed in both cases. For an addition of 10 wt.% of clay, the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy shows a maximum improvement of 52%, whereas the Cloisite 30B/epoxy shows a maximum of 80%. The improvement in elastic modulus can be directly correlated to the better dispersion and intercalation/exfoliation as observed in the latter case by TEM images (Figs. 3 and 4). In general, the improvement in elastic modulus is attributed to the good dispersion of nano-size clay particles that restrict the mobility of polymer chains under loading as well as to the good interfacial adhesion between the particles and the epoxy matrix [4].

Fig. 4. Effect of clay content on the mechanical properties of nanocomposites. (a) elastic modulus and (b) tensile strength

The orientation of silicate layers and polymer chains with respect to the loading direction can also contribute to the reinforcement effects [11]. However, the decreasing rate of elastic modulus improvement with higher clay content can be attributed to the presence of unexfoliated aggregates [11].

The variation in tensile strength with clay content is shown in Fig. 4b. Unlike the elastic modulus, both types of nanocomposites show a lower tensile strength than that of pure epoxy. Furthermore, both nanocomposites show similar tensile strength values irrespective of clay type and clay content. The lower tensile strength values than that of pure epoxy coincide with the results observed by Zerda et al. [6] but contrast to others reported elsewhere [4,11,12]. In the present study, these lower strengths can be assumed to be compounding process related. The compounding of clay nanoparticles in an epoxy matrix with a three-roll mill produces a highly viscous and foamy material, and the higher the clay content the higher the viscosity. Furthermore, both Nanomer I.28E and Cloisite® 30B particles treated with ammonium ions accelerate the curing process of epoxy resin and favor the delamination of clay platelets [13-14]. Therefore, the solution becomes highly viscous with mixing time and hinders the complete degassing before casting. It is also observed that the degassing problem becomes critical for nanocomposites containing more than 5 wt.% of clay, which in turn, produces nanocomposites with nano to micro-level voids [8,10]. The other source of voids could be trapped air during pouring of highly viscous material onto the mold. The failure of all specimens at the same strength level (25 to 40 MPa) also indicates the possibility of crack initiation from similar type of defects. Therefore under tensile loading, cracks can initiate from these tiny voids and cause the specimen to fail at relatively low strain.

Figure 5 shows the fracture surfaces of nanocomposites reinforced with both types of clay. The bright spots correspond to clay aggregates finely dispersed in the material. This observation further confirms the incomplete exfoliation or inevitable aggregation of clay layers in this type of nanocomposites. The presence of such clay aggregates in the microstructure of nanocomposite is also reported by Kornmann et al. [7]. These loose clusters or unexfoliated nanoparticles in the matrix may act as additional crack initiation sites by splitting up easily under applied load [6]. A better degassing and exfoliation technique is, therefore, very important and a preliminary result of better degassing has already shown improved tensile strength of clay/epoxy nanocomposites [10].

Fig. 5. SEM fractographs of 1 wt.% clay nanocomposites. (a) Nanomer I.28E (b) Cloisite® 30B

Thermomechanical Behavior

Figures 6a and 6b show the variation of storage modulus with temperature for both Nanomer I.28E- and Cloisite® 30B/epoxy nanocomposites, respectively. At 30°C, both types of nanocomposites show higher storage modulus as the clay content increases. However, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy nanocomposites show higher storage modulus than the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy for the same amount of clay content. As the temperature increases, both types of nanocomposites show a gradual drop in storage modulus up to the glass transition temperature where a sudden drop in the storage modulus is observed. However, for the same amount of clay content, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy nanocomposites show higher modulus at the glass transition temperatures than the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy nanocomposites. For an addition of 10 wt.% of clay, the Cloisite 30B/epoxy shows an improvement of 53%, whereas the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy shows about 22%. This signifies that the effect of clay on the thermomechanical behavior is less pronounced than that observed on the tensile behavior. This may be attributed to the frictional effect of clay nanoparticles under tensile loading, which is absent at elevated temperatures. The storage modulus (E') and glass transition temperature (T_g) of nanocomposites for various clay contents is shown in Table 2.

Fig. 6. Storage modulus versus temperature for: (a) Nanomer I.28E/epoxy (b) Cloisite 30B/epoxy.

Table 2. Effect of clay content on the storage modulus (E') and T_g .

Clay content (wt.%)	Nanomer I.28E/epoxy		Cloisite® 30B/epoxy	
	E' (GPa)	T_g (°C)	E' (GPa)	T_g (°C)
0	2.75	150	2.75	150
1	2.90	140	2.90	128
2	2.90	127	3.05	140
3	3.05	128	3.00	128
5	3.25	123	3.50	114
7	3.35	126	3.55	116
10	3.35	120	4.20	115

In general, the gradual drop in modulus is related to bending and stretching of cross-links as well as movements in the side chains or adjacent atoms in the main chain, whereas the sudden drop is related to the material transition from a glassy state to a rubbery state. Since epoxy is a thermosetting polymer, the transition occurs across a thermal band rather than at a distinct temperature. Agag et al. [16] reported higher T_g for polyimide-clay nanocomposites with higher clay contents. However, in the present study, T_g was found to decrease continuously with increasing clay content with respect to that of pure epoxy (150°C). A similar behavior is also reported by many researchers [17-18]. Since the glass transition process is related to the molecular motion, T_g is considered to be affected by molecular packing, chain rigidity and linearity [19]. Since the clay particles have extremely high specific surface area (750 m²/g), the good dispersion even at low clay contents provides an enormous amount of interfacial area. Therefore, the interaction of the polymer chains with the surface of the particles can drastically alter the chain kinetics in the regions surrounding them and lead to lower cross-link densities. Another possible reason for the decrease in T_g could be the lack of curing agent between clay platelets although this requires further study.

CONCLUSIONS

The compounding of nanoclay composites with a three-roll mill machine is found to produce both intercalated and exfoliated structures. While the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy shows an ordered intercalated structure with an average d-spacing of 3.6 nm, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy shows a disordered intercalated structure with an average d-spacing greater than 5 nm regardless of clay content. This can be attributed to the type of clay and its surface modification. Consistently, the Cloisite® 30B/epoxy nanocomposites show higher elastic modulus compared to the Nanomer I.28E/epoxy nanocomposites. This confirms the direct relation between the degree of exfoliation and mechanical properties of such materials. However, the apparent lower tensile strength of the nanocomposites with respect to that of pure epoxy can be attributed to the clay aggregates as well as to the nano to micro-size voids in the microstructure generated due to inadequate degassing of the solution. The storage modulus was also found to improve with higher clay content. However, the glass transition temperature decreased consistently for both types of nanocomposites regardless of clay content.

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